

STUDY OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS OF EAST SIKKIM

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ABSTRACT

Work-life balance, a term not so recent in origin has been in use since 1980s and implies how efficiently an individual prioritizes his/her personal and professional lives. Although the idea of having a perfect balance between work and life would seem rather elusive yet the benefits it entails in terms of better health, increased productivity and overall improved well-being need not be exaggerated. Sound work-life balance equation is a pre-requisite for better performance in any profession and therefore its relevance in teaching profession also cannot be denied. Teaching learning scenario has witnessed a shift from conventional teacher-dominated classroom to student-oriented and more constructivist learning environments. In the backdrop of these pertinent issues, the present paper focuses on work-life balance situation of secondary school teachers of East Sikkim with regard to certain demographic variables. A sample of 140 teachers was selected through simple random sampling technique and work-life balance tool of Hayman (2005) was used for collection of data which was analyzed in SPSS version 20. The study revealed no significant difference in the work-life balance of secondary school teachers with regard to gender. On the contrary, a significant difference was found in the work-life balance of teachers with regard to management and experience in WPLE dimension of work-life balance. The study suggests developing strategies to help teachers to maintain a proper work-life balance and thus contribute effectively for proper teaching learning.

Keywords : Work-life balance, secondary school teachers, gender, management, experience.

Introduction

Striking a balance between professional and personal life is bit of a challenge for any employee engaged in any kind of activity in today's world characterized by competition, advanced technology and fast pace (Halder & Sarkar p.669). Work-life balance is the degree to which an individual is involved in and satisfied equally with his/her job and personal roles and thus is a concept which involves proper prioritization between work and life i.e. career and family. It thus refers to the employees' ability to maintain a healthy balance between their work roles, personal responsibilities and family life (Kar & Misra, 2013). Ideal work-life balance can thus be achieved only when there is proper prioritization between work-life and personal life in such

a manner that an individual feel equally engaged and satisfied with both the domains. However difficult it may seem, it is essential to have a balance between one's work life and personal life because in it rests many other vital issues like: performance, effectiveness, satisfaction and most importantly feel-good factor.

Contemporary times is characterized by the advanced technology which allows a person to work from home and thus resulting in changed work culture, rise in dual earning couples as opposed to male member as the sole bread-winner of the family, increased workload and competition at the workplace striving to achieve excellence and quality and all these have consequently increased the work-load of employees. If the problem is narrowed down in case of teachers is observed that

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teachers are exposed to a great deal of pressure as routine class-taking, checking assignments, maintaining registers does not sum up the role of teachers. Besides these conventional roles teachers today are expected to perform multiple activities often excluded from their job description and thus become victims of imbalanced work-life equation. According to Akanni & Uduaran (2017) the nature of academic work has undergone a change as it has become more hectic for teachers who struggle to strike a balance between teaching, shouldering administrative responsibilities while simultaneously fulfilling the basic requirements regarding their promotion and vertical development.

Review of past literature

Ramanathan & Vanitha (2011) found that secondary level teachers in India face heavy work-life imbalances due to inflexible workload and working hours, students' behaviour modification and personal issues. It was also found that teachers with more years of teaching experience were able to balance their work and life however the study found that female teachers faced a great deal of work-life balance problems. The studies of Tanoi, Mizumoto & Okubo (2012) revealed that junior high school teachers invest their time in work and found that long working hours and inappropriate time use resulted in role conflict among teachers and they concluded that this role conflict is due to lack of work-life balance. Thus, their study concluded that junior high school teachers in Japan are in a difficult position. Uddin, Mamun, Hoque & Uddin (2013) found out that 59 percent female teachers replied that their jobs disturbed them in providing time to their family. Whereas, 44 percent respondents replied that their personal or familial life disturbed them in doing their jobs perfectly. Therefore, the study revealed that both family and job of female teachers of Bangladesh are being affected due to work-life balance situation. Saravanan & Dharani (2014) found female private school teachers to have more balanced work life situation than their male counterparts. Sharma & Agarwal (2017) found male teachers to have better work-life balance than their female counterparts. Aliasgar (2017) found a significant difference in the quality of work-life balance of male and female teachers,

no significant difference in the quality of work-life balance of teachers having less than ten years and more than ten years of teaching experience and also no significant difference in the quality of work life balance of secondary school teachers teaching in government, private- aided and private- unaided schools.

Significance of the study

The idea of teaching -learning has undergone tremendous change as teachers are required to perform many other activities besides lesson delivery and this has added up to the task of teachers. If the problem is viewed in context of Sikkim it is seen that schools throughout Sikkim are engaged in several activities keeping in tune with the idea of excelling towards quality. This has however increased the workload of teachers who struggle to maintain balance between their work and personal lives. Hence in the light of these issues the investigators were keen to understand the work-life balance situation of secondary school teachers of East Sikkim. The study can be significant enough to explore the work-life balance situation of teachers and thus devise some workplace strategies in helping teachers maintain sound work –life balance condition.

Statement of the Problem

Holistic development of learners, one of the important aims of education is not achieved by mere content delivery by the teachers rather it requires them to take care of other vital issues besides knowledge giving which constantly keeps the teachers occupied. The increased workload at the workplace as well as household responsibilities including dependent care somewhat leave the teachers with less time to nourish their personal needs and consequently leads to imbalanced work-life equation. Hence the problem is stated as “**Study of Work-Life Balance of Secondary School Teachers of East Sikkim.**”

Main Objective of the study

To study the work-life balance of secondary school teachers of East Sikkim in relation to gender, management and experience.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in work-life balance between male and female secondary

school teachers of East Sikkim.

2. There is no significant difference in the work-life balance between government and private secondary school teachers of East Sikkim.
3. There is no significant difference in work life balance between secondary school teachers of East Sikkim having less ten years, ten to twenty years and more than twenty years of teaching experience.

Operational Definition of the Terms Used

Work-life balance- refers to the ability of teachers to maintain a balance between their work responsibilities, personal life responsibilities and family responsibilities.

Secondary school teachers- secondary school teachers in the present study refers to teachers teaching in class IX and X.

Delimitation of the study

Owing to certain constraints the present study was delimited to only 140 teachers of East Sikkim teaching at the secondary level.

Sample and sampling technique

Sample for the present study comprised of 140 secondary school teachers teaching in various secondary schools of East Sikkim was selected. Descriptive Research Method was adopted in the present study and Simple random sampling was used as a technique of selecting the sample.

Tool Used

In the present study, the investigators have used Hayman Work-life Balance Scale (2005).

Results

Assuming the normality of the distribution of the scores, for the present study, the investigators used descriptive statistics i.e. mean, SD, as well parametric tests i.e. t-test and F test for analysis of the data.

Null Hypothesis 1:

“There is no significant difference in work-life balance between male and female secondary school teachers of East Sikkim.”

Table 1

Comparison of Work-Life balance across Gender

Dimensions of								
Work-life Balance	Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' value	p value	Significance level	
Work interference with personal life (WIPL)	Male	56	4.66	0.87	-0.65	0.52	Not Significant at 0.05 level	
	Female	84	4.77	0.97				
Personal Life Interference with Work (PLIW)	Male	56	5.42	1.17	-0.88	0.38	Not Significant at 0.05 level	
	Female	84	5.59	1.06				
Work Personal Life Enhancement (WPLE)	Male	56	5.47	1.2	1.46	0.15	Not Significant at 0.05 level	
	Female	84	5.19	0.91				
Overall Work-Life Balance	Male	56	5.08	0.71	-0.16	0.87	Not Significant at 0.05 level	
	Female	84	5.1	0.72				

It is clear from the table (1) that for all the dimensions the computed value of 't' is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. i.e. WIPL has $t(138) = -0.65$, $p = 0.52$ for PLIW has $t(138) = -0.88$, $p = 0.38$ as for WPLE has $t(138) = 1.46$, $p = 0.15$. The above results thus imply that there is no significant difference between male and female teachers of East Sikkim in any dimensions of work-life balance. Similarly, the above table also indicates that there is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers of Sikkim in

their overall work-life balance as $t(138) = -0.16$, $p = 0.87$ is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the investigators fail to reject H_{01} and conclude that there is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers on all the three dimensions of work-life balance.

Null Hypothesis 2:

“There is no significant difference in the work-life balance between government and private secondary school teachers of East Sikkim.”

Table 2
Comparison of Work-Life balance across Management

Dimensions of Work-life Balance	Management	N	Mean	SD	't' value	p value	Significance level
Work interference with personal life (WIPL)	Government	100	4.65	0.9	-1.47	0.14	Not Significant at 0.05 level
	Private	40	4.91	0.98			
Personal Life Interference with Work (PLIW)	Government	100	5.37	1.08	-2.78	0.01	Significant at 0.05 level
	Private	40	5.93	1.08			
Work Personal Life Enhancement (WPLE)	Government	100	5.25	0.99	-1.05	0.29	Not Significant at 0.05 level
	Private	40	5.45	1.54			
Overall Work-Life Balance	Government	100	5	0.68	-2.46	0.02	Significant at 0.05 level
	Private	40	5.32	0.75			

It is clear from the table (2) that there is a significant difference between government and private school teachers on the second dimension of work-life

balance i.e. PLIW where the computed value of t is $t(138) = -2.78$, $p = 0.00$ which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. However, for the first dimension the

calculated value of 't' $t(138)=-1.47, p=0.14$ which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance and government school and private school teachers also did not differ significantly in the third dimension as the computed value for this dimension as $t(138)=-1.05, p=0.29$ is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the table implies that government and private school teachers differ in terms of and personal life interference with work where by government school teachers experience more instances of work interference with personal life and vice-versa than private school teachers. Whereas, they do not differ significantly with regard to their opinions on work interference with personal life and work personal

life enhancement. The above also indicates a significant difference between government and private school teachers in their work-life balance as the computed value is $t(138)=-2.46, p=0.02$. Hence it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between government school and private school teachers on work-life balance and hence H_{02} that there is no significant difference in the work-life balance between government and private secondary school teachers of East Sikkim is rejected.

Null Hypothesis 3 :

“There is no significant difference in work life balance between secondary school teachers of East Sikkim having less ten years, ten to twenty years and more than twenty years of teaching experience.”

Table 3
Comparison of Work-Life Balance across Experience

Dimensions of		N	Mean	SD	F value	p value	Significance level
Work-life Balance	Experience						
Work interference with personal life (WIPL)	Less than ten years	75	4.77	0.87	0.29	0.75	Not Significant at 0.05 level
	Between 10-20 years	38	4.63	1			
	Above 20 years	27	4.72	1			
	Total	140	4.73	0.93			
Personal Life Interference with Work (PLIW)	Less than ten years	75	5.62	1.09	0.6	0.55	Not Significant at 0.05 level
	Between 10-20 years	38	5.43	1.13			
	Above 20 years	27	5.4	1.11			
	Total	140	5.53	1.1			

Work Personal Life Enhancement (WPLE)	Less than ten years	75	5.2	1.14	3.32	0.04	Significant at 0.05 level
	Between 10-20 years	38	5.18	0.83			
	Above 20 years	27	5.76	0.92			
	Total	140	5.3	1.04			
Overall Work-life Balance	Less than ten years	75	5.11	0.69	0.62	0.54	Not Significant at 0.05 level
	Between 10-20 years	38	4.99	0.74			
	Above 20 years	27	5.18	0.75			
	Total	140	5.09	0.71			

It can be inferred from the table (3) that the teachers having less than ten years and between ten-twenty years, as well as above twenty years of teaching experience did not differ significantly in the first two dimensions of work-life balance. The value of F for the first dimension is $F(2,137)=0.29$, $p=0.75$ therefore it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the work-life balance of secondary school teachers of East Sikkim on the first dimension based on their years of teaching experience. Likewise, the value of F for the second dimension is $F(2,117)=0.60$, $p=0.55$ which indicates no significant difference in the work-life balance of secondary school teachers of East Sikkim on the second dimension of work-life balance tool. Secondary school teachers of East Sikkim having different years of teaching experience however differed significantly in the third dimension of the work-life

balance tool as the calculated value of F is $F(2,117)=3.32$, $p=0.04$ which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The table also indicates that there is no significant difference between teachers having varying degrees of teaching experience in their overall work-life balance as the value of F i.e. $F(2,137)=0.62$, $p=0.54$ which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance therefore on perusal of the above table it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between secondary school teachers having varying degrees of experience on work-life balance and thus the investigator fails to reject H_0 that there is no significant difference in work life balance between secondary school teachers of East Sikkim having less ten years, ten to twenty years and more than twenty years of teaching experience. Therefore, on the basis of the above results alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Table 4

Post Hoc Test results for Work-Life Balance vs Work Personal Life Enhancement

Experience(I)	Experience(J)	Mean Difference(I-J)	Std. Error	sig.	95% confidence interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
< 10 years	> 20 years	-056	0.23	0.04	-1.10	-0.01

Significant at 0.05 level

Table (4) depicts the Tukey HSD, post-hoc test results of secondary school teachers of East Sikkim in terms of work personal life enhancement. The table indicates a significant difference among secondary school teachers of East Sikkim having less than ten years of teaching experience and teachers having more than twenty years of teaching experience as p value of 0.04 is significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Findings and Discussion

The present study revealed no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers on all the three dimensions of work-life balance i.e. WIPL, PLIW and WPLE. This finding contradicts with the findings of Ramanathan & Vanitha (2011); Sharma & Agarwal (2017); Uddin, Mamun, Hoque & Uddin (2013) who reported female teachers to have poor work-life balance. The finding points to the fact that in Sikkimese society both male and female carry equal amount of responsibilities and issues of gender inequality is not so rampant in Sikkim. Women in Sikkim have enjoyed equal entitlements and privileges like their male counterparts and thus the present finding does not come as a surprise. The study reported a significant difference between government and private school teachers with regard to PLIW as well as on overall WLB. Private school teachers seemed to enjoy better work-life condition than their government counterparts. Currently in Sikkim government schools throughout the state have engaged in many extra activities besides teaching which keeps them busy resulting in their failure to manage time resulting in work-life imbalances. However, teachers from both type of management believed that both work and life can enhance and complement each other. This finding contradicts with the finding of Aliasgar (2017) who did not report any significant difference between teachers teaching under different types of management.

The study also found that teachers having varying years of teaching experience showed significant no significant difference in terms of overall work-life balance as well as in the first two dimensions i.e. WIPL, PLIW. This finding coincides with the study of Aliasgar (2017) who reported a similar finding of no significant impact of teaching experience on the work life balance of

teachers. However, a significant difference was found with regard to WPLE. Teachers having more than twenty years of teaching experience opined more work and personal life enhancing each other as compared to teachers with less than ten years of teaching experience.

Conclusion

On the basis of the findings it can be concluded that government schools can develop some strategies for minimizing the issues of poor work-life balance of their staff because in Sikkim it is observed that government schools are engaged in many activities which keeps the teachers on their toes all the time. Focus should be on enabling teachers to have proper time management so that there is no overlapping of work demands and personal demands. Since the study pointed to the existence of difference in perception of less experienced and more experienced teachers in terms of how work and personal life complement each other, the investigators recommend for motivating and encouraging younger teachers to view work and personal life as complementing rather than competing with each other. Attitudinal change can effectively contribute in harmonizing work and life with each other, rather than viewing them as opposites. Workplace strategies in the form of flexi-time, more lenient rules in terms of leave, inclusion of spiritual programmes like yoga for relaxation can go a long way in ensuring sound work-life balance for teachers.

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